

A SYSTEMATIC STUDY OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE UNIT CELLS BASED ON GEOMETRIC MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

While textile reinforced composite materials are commonly employed in structural applications, many design analysis methods incorporate a number of fundamental assumptions which do not permit an accurate description of the mechanical behaviour of the material with respect to the textile architecture. A comprehensive systematic study of the effects of geometric and material parameters on both elastic and failure behaviour is presently being undertaken using finite element (FE) analysis of unit cells, and results from this study are presented in this paper. The initial aim is to provide an indication of sensitivity to these parameters, while the long term goal is to develop a fully predictive modelling approach to evaluate new textile reinforcements at the design stage, and to enable semi-automated mechanical property prediction of textile composites at different volume fractions and after the reinforcement has been deformed (draped) to cover curved surfaces. The unit cell FE technique minimises the number of assumptions required, and permits investigation of behaviour under biaxial loading.

KEYWORDS: unit cell model, mechanical properties, finite element analysis, angle-ply laminate

NOMENCLATURE

Symbols

E	Young's modulus
G	shear modulus
ν	Poisson's ratio
σ	stress
τ	shear stress
ϵ	strain
γ	engineering shear strain
V_f	fibre volume fraction
a	aspect ratio (width/height)
n	tow shape geometric parameter
r	fibre radius
s	fibre spacing (pitch) assuming square packing of fibres in the composite
x	loading direction of bi-directional laminate
w	width
h	height
ϕ	ply angle (angle between tows and loading direction)

Subscripts

f	property of fibre
m	property of matrix
t	property of tow
c	property of cell
u	ultimate (i.e. failure) stress
1	primary axis of a unidirectional lamina (parallel to fibre direction)
2	transverse axis of a unidirectional lamina (perpendicular to the fibre direction, in the plane of the lamina)
3	through-thickness axis of a unidirectional lamina

INTRODUCTION

Considerable research is undertaken into the mechanical performance of composites, and a significant subset of this work pertains to textile reinforced materials. Textile reinforced composites typically offer good mechanical properties together with relatively low material and processing costs. While they are in widespread use, there is no single accepted method to determine elastic and failure behaviour of

textile composites which can be applied to all situations. Textile models exist which have the ability to describe a broad range of woven and braided textiles, and even to determine the shape of the dry textile using mechanical methods [1], however generation of the complex resin volumes surrounding the tows is often very difficult, limiting the ease of application for analysis of the final composite. This problem can be addressed by some solid modelling methods and initial models of such unit cells have been reported [2]. Mechanical behaviour of textile composites is often determined using analytical techniques [3]. While these offer minimal computational costs, they typically rely on assumptions such as isostress or isostrain, which are inherently simplifications of the true scenario. Some researchers [4,5] have developed detailed models of textile repeating units for stress analysis, which offer improved results but are frequently restricted to a limited selection of textile architectures [6,7], although some of these can account for reinforcement deformation during forming [8]. Some models offer predictive capabilities for biaxial failure behaviour but require uniaxial mechanical characterisation of the material [9]. Other researchers [10] have performed multi-scale modelling for simulation of pre-preg or thermoplastic composite sheet forming. There is no complete solution which can model general textile architectures, accounting for variability and for deformation during forming, allowing near-automated generation of solid mechanical models on a purely predictive basis.

The work presented in this paper is part of a collective effort towards fully automated modelling of general textile architectures [11], many of the algorithms having been described previously [12,13]. Not only is it possible to model different weave styles, but each geometric parameter (tow cross-section, tow spacing, crimp etc.) within a model of a textile may be modified easily. Statistical variation of fabric architecture may also be incorporated using an appropriate distribution. Models of textiles having undergone in-plane shear deformation during forming may also be generated. A robust algorithm to generate the complex resin volumes enables geometric modelling of the entire composite unit cell. Using three dimensional FE analysis of composite unit cells (meso-scale) generated with this model permits prediction of mechanical properties within different areas of draped components made from many different fabrics accounting for their natural variability. Properties obtained in this manner will be used as input data for FE analysis at the part level (macro-scale).

Before proceeding with a large number of computationally intensive studies into various textile structures, it is important to have a clear understanding of the individual effects of different material properties and of geometric parameters. Such work is presented in this paper using analysis of two dimensional cross-sections through a single tow. Effects of various parameters are evaluated and their sensitivity in analysis of stiffness and failure in transverse tension is reported. Preliminary results from solid models of angle-ply laminates are also presented together with comparable experimental data.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITE TOW

For the purposes of this paper, only glass fibre reinforced polyester composites are considered, although the method presented may be applied to other fibre/matrix systems with little modification. Micromechanical models are used to determine mechanical behaviour of the unidirectional composite which forms the tows. The rule of mixtures is used for Young's modulus in the fibre direction and for Poisson's ratio, while the Halpin-Tsai equations are used to calculate transverse and shear moduli. The application of these equations to the materials in question is described elsewhere [14]. Since the polyester resin has a lower strain to failure than the glass fibre reinforcement, the ultimate strength in the fibre direction is considered to be fibre dominated according to Equation (1).

$$\sigma_{1ut} = V_f \sigma_{uf} \quad (1)$$

Transverse tensile strength within the tow is predicted using a micromechanics model which evaluates stress concentration induced by the presence of stiff cylindrical fibres within the matrix. Consequently, the transverse failure stress is given by Equation (2).

$$\sigma_{2ut} = \frac{\sigma_{um}}{k_{\sigma 2}} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{um} is the matrix failure stress and $k_{\sigma 2}$ is the stress concentration factor for transverse stress, which is given by Equation (3), after [15].

$$k_{\sigma 2} = \frac{E_m}{E_{2t} \left(\frac{2r}{s} \left[\frac{E_m}{E_f} - 1 \right] + 1 \right)} \quad (3)$$

where E_m , E_f & E_{2t} are Young's moduli of matrix, fibre and tow respectively, r is the fibre radius and s is the spacing between the fibres (assuming square packing).

The same micromechanics model is used for shear strength of the unidirectional composite in the 2-3 plane (τ_{23ut}), substituting shear moduli G_m , G_f & G_t for the appropriate Young's moduli in Equation (3). In the absence of a simple model for in-plane shear strength, a constant value of $\tau_{12ut} = \tau_{13ut} = 50\text{Mpa}$ is assumed, after [16].

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The systematic study presented in this paper concentrates on the effect of various parameters on transverse tensile behaviour of composites, i.e. behaviour when load is applied perpendicular to the fibre direction. Models of a single tow cross-section in the 2-3 plane within a rectangular cell are made in two dimensions, and quadratic triangular generalised plane strain elements are employed within the Abaqus implicit FE code (element designation CPEG6). These elements permit through-thickness strain, but require this to remain constant for the whole model, i.e. faces remain plane but may move in the material 1 direction. Unit thickness is assumed. Displacement is applied to the right hand vertical edge in the 2 direction, while the left hand vertical edge is restrained in the 2 direction. Both vertical edges are free to move in the 3 direction. The lower edge is free to move in the 2 direction and restrained in the 1 direction. The upper edge is free to move in both directions, but forced to remain flat by coupling the displacement degree of freedom in the 3 direction for all nodes on this edge using the *EQUATION option in Abaqus. The axis system is defined in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Specification of material axes used for FE modelling

The transverse modulus of the cell, E_{2c} , is calculated by obtaining the applied strain in the cell, ϵ_{2c} , from the prescribed displacement and cell length according to Equation (4), and the resultant stress, σ_{2c} , from the sum of the reaction forces in the 2 direction at the nodes on the edge where displacement is applied and the cross-sectional area in the 1-3 plane, as in Equation (5). This enables direct calculation of the effective modulus of the cell using Equation (6).

$$\epsilon_{2c} = \frac{\delta w_c}{w_c} \quad (4)$$

where w_c is the width of the unit cell and δw_c is the prescribed displacement (Figure 2)

$$\sigma_{2c} = \frac{\sum RF_2}{h_c} \quad (\text{assuming unit thickness in the 1 direction}) \quad (5)$$

where h_c is the height of the unit cell and $\sum RF_2$ is the total reaction force at the displaced edge (Figure 2)

$$E_{2c} = \frac{\sigma_{2c}}{\varepsilon_{2c}} \quad (6)$$

Failure stress for the cell is determined using the Maximum Stress failure criterion within the tow and the von Mises criterion in the resin. The Maximum Stress criterion states that if any of the principal stresses exceeds the corresponding failure stress then failure is deemed to occur; for the isotropic resin phase, the von Mises stress invariant is compared with the resin failure stress to determine whether failure occurs. A failure index is calculated at each integration point using a user subroutine within Abaqus according to Equations (7) and (8). Since the analysis is linear, the maximum failure index obtained in the model is proportional to the prescribed displacement and hence to the resultant stress, enabling the initial failure stress to be determined directly.

$$FI_t = \max \left(\left| \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1ut}} \right|, \left| \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_{2ut}} \right|, \left| \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{3ut}} \right|, \left| \frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12ut}} \right|, \left| \frac{\tau_{13}}{\tau_{13ut}} \right|, \left| \frac{\tau_{23}}{\tau_{23ut}} \right| \right) \quad (7)$$

$$FI_m = \frac{\sigma_{vonMises}}{\sigma_{um}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 2 Dimensions of the 2D unit cell model, displaced shape shown with dashed line.

Initial results from 3D solid models are also presented. Simple models of angle-ply laminates have been constructed for illustrative purposes at this stage. Solid meshes have been generated using tetrahedral elements (designation C3D4) and run for cases of tension applied in the bias direction. Orthotropic material properties are entered for the tow regions (with appropriate material orientations specified) to give values of Vf_c of approximately 38%.

PLANNING OF ANALYSES

A systematic evaluation of sensitivity of the model to a number of material and geometric parameters has been undertaken. In preparing this evaluation, a number of independent geometric parameters were identified; by modifying their value a large array of unit cells representing parts of actual preforms can be created. In each simulation the values taken by these parameters are selected with the purpose of highlighting their individual effects from minimal computational effort.

The long-term aim of this work is to document the effect on mechanical properties of all parameters used in defining any unit-cell from within a full 3D multi-layer preform. The systematic way to proceed towards this aim is to start with single tow sections in 2D, progress to multiple tow sections forming single textile layers, and subsequently to multiple tow sections forming multiple textile layers.

Conclusions from the 2D work will form a basis from which systematic 3D work will be initiated for single layers of complex textiles, and finally for superimposed ones.

Taguchi [17] planning is being used throughout the work. Groups of simulations where only one parameter is varied are presented in this paper for illustrative purposes. The first task consists of identifying suitable independent parameters. Geometric parameters have been selected on the basis of independence with due consideration to practical reality. For example, the cell fibre volume fraction Vf_c (equal to the local fibre volume fraction of the composite) is a parameter since it may be controlled. Conversely, the tow fibre volume fraction Vf_t is not a parameter since in practice the number of fibres placed in the tool is changed; hence the latter parameter is selected for the investigation instead.

A formal means of representing the tow cross-section geometry in models of unit cells for FE analysis is required. The expression given in Equation (9) offers flexibility to modify not only the aspect ratio, but also the ratio of the area to that of its bounding rectangle (the area ratio).

$$y = \pm \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a_t^2} \right)^n \quad (9)$$

where a_t is the aspect ratio of the tow, while the power, n , affects the tow shape, hence changing the area ratio. For $n=0$ the shape is rectangular, while for $n=0.5$ an ellipse is generated. Coordinates are generated for each quadrant independently such that asymmetric shapes can be produced, although symmetric tow shapes are used exclusively for the results presented in this paper.

The tow width w_t and height h_t are defined along the 2 and 3 directions respectively (x and y in Equation (9)). The nominal geometric case has a tow width, w_t , of 5mm and aspect ratio (width/height), a_t , of 5. The tow width changes with aspect ratio such that the tow bounding box area ($w_t \times h_t$) remains constant. Tow cross-section is modified according to Equation (9). In this way, the fibre volume fraction within the tow remains independent of a_t . The power n , affects the general shape of the tow with $n=0.5$ corresponding to an ellipse and $n<0.5$ evolving towards a fuller, more rectangular shape; in the nominal case, $n=0.3$. The nominal case contains 10000 fibres of diameter 15.8 μm ; values in the range 6000-14000 were used within the study presented. These numbers were selected to produce reasonable fibre volume fractions within the tow and cell, values ranging between $0.25 < Vf_t < 0.70$ and $0.19 < Vf_c < 0.44$ respectively. Values selected for each parameter appear in Table 1.

The composite unit cell is defined as follows. The minimum dimensions for the rectangular cell are the tow width w_t and tow height h_t . From these dimensions a maximum value for the fibre volume fraction of the cell (or composite) $Vf_{c,max}$ can be obtained. Cell aspect ratio, a_c , remains equal to that of the tow, a_t , and cell width, w_c , is calculated such that $Vf_c = 0.9 \times Vf_{c,max}$ in all cases. This provides a reasonable area around the cell both in terms of a realistic representation of the composite and for practical issues related to mesh generation.

The 25 combinations of parameters selected for this study appear in Table 1. Further work is planned for single tows in 2D where the tow section is not symmetric, touches the domain boundaries, and is located away from the centre of the cell. Conclusions from this work will be used in defining further 2D work for tow sections assembled in single and multiple layers, which will, in turn, define parameters for investigation with 3D models.

Table 1 Parameters and results of 2D generalised plane strain FE analyses (parameter under investigation shown in bold for each case).

Simulation	Parameters						Results	
	Fibre modulus, E_f (GPa)	Matrix modulus, E_m (GPa)	Matrix failure stress, σ_{um} (MPa)	No. fibres	Tow aspect ratio, a_t	Tow shape parameter, n	E_2 (GPa)	σ_{2u} (MPa)
1 (nominal)	70	4	60	10000	5	0.3	8.37	34.11
2	60	4	60	10000	5	0.3	8.21	33.52
3	65	4	60	10000	5	0.3	8.29	33.84
4	75	4	60	10000	5	0.3	8.43	34.39
5	80	4	60	10000	5	0.3	8.49	34.60
6	70	3	60	10000	5	0.3	6.47	35.10
7	70	3.5	60	10000	5	0.3	7.43	34.60
8	70	4.5	60	10000	5	0.3	9.28	33.65
9	70	5	60	10000	5	0.3	10.16	33.17
10	70	4	40	10000	5	0.3	8.37	22.76
11	70	4	50	10000	5	0.3	8.37	28.45
12	70	4	70	10000	5	0.3	8.37	39.83
13	70	4	80	10000	5	0.3	8.37	45.52
14	70	4	60	6000	5	0.3	6.28	39.70
15	70	4	60	8000	5	0.3	7.25	36.99
16	70	4	60	12000	5	0.3	9.66	30.65
17	70	4	60	14000	5	0.3	11.19	26.07
18	70	4	60	10000	3	0.3	8.29	46.03
19	70	4	60	10000	4	0.3	8.35	35.70
20	70	4	60	10000	6	0.3	8.40	35.07
21	70	4	60	10000	7	0.3	8.42	34.94
22	70	4	60	10000	5	0.1	8.95	37.86
23	70	4	60	10000	5	0.2	8.63	37.54
24	70	4	60	10000	5	0.4	8.13	32.83
25	70	4	60	10000	5	0.5	7.92	30.34

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results are presented of transverse modulus, E_{2c} , and failure stress, σ_{2uc} , with respect to the parameters examined within the study. Results presented isolate individual variables as described in the planning section of the paper. In all of the two-dimensional cases studies, the failure mechanism is transverse tension within the tow region. This is in agreement with the experimental findings for plain-weave textile composites of Pandita et al.[18]. Figure 3 shows the effect of fibre modulus, E_f , on mechanical behaviour. It is clear from this that while E_f is well known to have a significant effect on properties in the fibre direction, it does not have such significance for the transverse properties.

Figure 3 Effect of fibre modulus on the elastic and failure behaviour of the unit cell.

Conversely, the Young's modulus of the matrix phase plays a much more significant role in the transverse elastic behaviour of the unit cell, as demonstrated in Figure 4. While this may be observed from the Halpin-Tsai equations, the effect on the failure behaviour of the cell is less obvious.

Figure 4 Effect of resin modulus on the elastic and failure behaviour of the unit cell.

Although the strength of the matrix phase has no direct influence on the composite elastic behaviour, it is the parameter with the most significant effect on the transverse failure stress; this is clear from Figure 5. The relationship between σ_{2uc} and σ_{um} is one of direct proportionality when all other parameters are maintained constant. As long as failure is known to be by transverse tension within the tow, this relationship can be deduced directly from Equation (2).

Figure 5 Effect of resin strength on the failure behaviour of the unit cell.

As discussed in the planning section, the number of fibres contained within the tow has been used to determine the fibre volume fraction of the tow, V_{f_t} , and the cell, V_{f_c} . In the cases presented in Figure 6, the relationship between the number of fibres and both V_{f_t} and V_{f_c} is proportional. If modulus is calculated for the whole cell using the Halpin-Tsai equations assuming an even distribution of fibres within the cell having fibre volume fraction, V_{f_c} , the results overlay those produced using the FE approach exactly in this case. If the same approach is used with the micromechanics model for σ_{2u} , however, the strength is considerably overestimated. This is clearly because the unit cell models employ a much higher volume fraction within the tow region, which subsequently fails at lower stresses. In most design analysis environments, however, this issue would almost certainly be overlooked.

Although the tow aspect ratio, a_t , (defined as tow width divided by tow height) has little effect on the elastic behaviour of the cell, and no effect on the fibre volume fraction, it can be seen from Figure 7 that a change in aspect ratio from 3 to 4 results in a reduction in failure stress of around 22%. This is a comparable reduction to that observed when the number of fibres (and hence V_{f_t} and V_{f_c}) is doubled. While no designer would ignore such a change in fibre volume fraction, it is most unlikely that the cross-section of the tow is even considered in such an environment. It may be argued that well designed composite components should not be susceptible to transverse failure modes. However, in many applications of textile reinforcements while one set of tows may carry the load along its principal

axis, there is often a perpendicular set of tows within which cracks may develop and spread to interlaminar regions, such as those observed in [18].

Figure 6 Effect of number of fibres on the elastic and failure behaviour of the unit cell. Failure behaviour observed in the FE model is compared with that determined by assuming a uniform fibre distribution within the unit cell having the same number of fibres using the micromechanics approach in Equation (2).

Figure 7 Effect of tow aspect ratio on the elastic and failure behaviour of the unit cell.

When the tow shape parameter, n , is changed, V_{f_t} changes while V_{f_c} remains constant. The volume fraction within the tow increases with increasing n due to the subsequent reduction in tow area. While increasing V_{f_t} has already been shown to reduce failure stress, it is still not obvious that the modulus would be reduced under the same circumstances, although the results presented in Figure 8 indicate that this is the case.

Figure 8 Effect of tow shape parameter on the elastic and failure behaviour of the unit cell.

Experimental testing of transverse mechanical behaviour of UD composites has been undertaken by the authors. Unidirectional tows assembled in a tricot-stitched fabric configuration were used to construct glass-polyester laminates at three fibre volume fractions. Results showed an increase in failure stress with fibre volume fraction within the laminate, which contradicts the predictions of micromechanics models for σ_{2u} as shown in Figure 9. It seems from the results presented in this paper, that this

phenomenon may be explained by changes in tow geometry which are not considered by more traditional approaches.

Figure 9 Experimental data for laminates manufactured from unidirectional glass fabric compared with micromechanics model which assumes an even distribution of fibres within the laminate & 2D FE of a single tow. Error bars show maximum and minimum values obtained during testing.

Figure 10 shows values of effective modulus in the bias direction obtained using FE of solid unit cells of non-crimp angle-ply laminates. Experimental data from similar laminates at the same fibre volume fraction are also presented and reasonable agreement is noted. Distribution of principal stress is shown for a $\pm 60^\circ$ laminate subjected to bias tension in Figure 11.

Figure 10 Experimental data for modulus of angle-ply laminates presented with comparable data obtained using FE analysis of solid unit cells. Error bars show maximum and minimum values obtained during testing. Experimental method was presented in [19]

Figure 11 Distribution of principal stress value σ_1 (MPa) observed using FE analysis of solid unit cell (upper layer of resin removed for visualisation); $\pm 60^\circ$ angle-ply laminate

CONCLUSIONS

A method is presented to assess sensitivity of composite transverse behaviour to a number of material and geometric parameters using two dimensional, generalised plane strain elements within an implicit FE code. This method is employed to enable quick determination of the significance of each variable before conducting a series of time consuming and computationally expensive three dimensional analyses of textile composite repeating unit cells. Results show phenomena which are ignored using conventional analysis techniques. Experimental data which contradict micromechanics models for transverse strength are presented, with the suggestion that geometric features of the reinforcement may have greater significance in these cases than the bulk fibre volume fraction.

Initial results from solid models are presented, illustrating stress distributions within unit cells of angle-ply laminates. Effective modulus of these models is also presented together with comparable experimental data.

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